

Quantitative Structure–Activity Relationship (QSAR) approach for oxygen evolution reaction in heterogeneous electrocatalysis: toward reliable statistical prediction of catalytic overpotentials

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ABSTRACT. Water electrolyzers are electrochemical devices that split liquid water into its fundamental components, and they are subjected to constant and rigorous improvements to meet the increasing demands in production of green hydrogen for clean energy purposes. Oxygen evolution reaction (OER), the half-reaction producing O₂, is kinetically slower than hydrogen evolution reaction (HER), the half-reaction producing H₂, and it is a well-known source of substantial overpotential and sluggish performances in water electrolyzers. A viable solution to improve this technology involves the preparation of targeted catalytic materials able to deliver lower OER overpotentials. Catalytic design is challenging, however, and synthetic trial-and-error strategy and stability tests may not be economically and environmentally sustainable. Hence, a model able to predict *a priori* OER overpotentials of unexplored materials is unquestionably a game changer. In the present work, chemometrics, Quantitative Structure-Activity Relationship (QSAR) and Organization for Economic Co-operation and Development (OECD) principles, have been successfully employed to select statistically relevant variables, or descriptors, affecting OER performances of particle solid catalysts in lab-scale experiments, build a robust training and an external evaluation set, and deliver a user-friendly predictive model. Such model delivers excellent and reliable predictions of OER overpotentials with a remarkable standard error of the prediction of $\approx \pm 45-48$ mV for “unknown-to-the-model” materials, that have been “blindly” picked from literature, but not included in either training or internal evaluation sets.

INTRODUCTION

The complete electrochemical process in an alkaline water electrolyzer ($2\text{H}_2\text{O}_{(l)} \rightarrow 2\text{H}_{2(g)} + \text{O}_{2(g)}$) is a combination of two separate half reactions: the oxygen evolution reaction (OER) ($4\text{OH}^-_{(aq)} \rightarrow \text{O}_{2(g)} + 2\text{H}_2\text{O}_{(l)} + 4e^-$) and the hydrogen evolution reaction (HER) ($4\text{H}_2\text{O}_{(l)} + 4e^- \rightarrow 2\text{H}_{2(g)} + 4\text{OH}^-_{(aq)}$), which occur at the anode and cathode sides of the

electrochemical cell, respectively. OER, as a multielectron transfer reaction, is kinetically much slower than HER.¹ Such bottleneck may be improved, if not overcome, by finding a suitable catalyst that improves the kinetics of the OER reaction and, thus, the overall performance of the device. RuO₂ and IrO₂ are considered state-of-the-art OER catalysts,² but their high costs and scarcity in nature have triggered the exploration of cheaper and more abundant catalyst materials.¹ A reliable and relevant electrochemical parameter to compare the catalytic performances of different OER catalysts is the overpotential (η_{10} , in mV).²⁻⁴ Experimentally, the overpotential is an additional potential required with respect to the standard potential of water electrolysis, -1.23 V at 25 °C,⁵ whose application is required to generate a specified current density.⁶ The greater this additional potential is, the lower are usually the performances in terms of electrocatalytic conversion and power consumption of the electrochemical device. Various factors can influence the value of overpotential, starting from the choice of the experimental set up to the choice of the catalytic material.

The comprehension of the relationship between catalyst structure/properties and catalytic activity is a key aspect to improve the performance of electrochemical devices and processes with technological and industrial interest. To obtain such understanding, the implementation of chemometric and Quantitative Structure–Activity Relationship (QSAR) methodologies serve as a crucial tool. Chemometrics is the discipline that applies mathematical and statistical methods to solve multivariate problems in chemistry. QSAR methods are a branch of chemometrics focusing on building quantitative models that correlate the chemical structure with a selected response to predict properties of new chemicals.

The application of chemometrics and QSAR models is well established in pharmaceutical chemistry, environmental, and food science as a tool to boost drug discovery, optimization of experimental procedures, risk assessment, and safety evaluation.⁷⁻¹⁰ In recent years, QSAR models have also been employed in the field of nanotechnology and nanomaterials to evaluate

the toxicity and risks related to the use of nanoparticles and other nanomaterials on living organisms, the so called nano-QSAR models.¹¹

The implementation of chemometric and statistical methods in electrochemistry is quite challenging, due to the dynamic nature of the electroanalytical methods and the mathematical complexity required by the treatment of electrochemical data.^{10, 12} There are several interesting exploratory studies reported in literature on the prediction of OER overpotential or activity *via* statistical techniques, volcano plots and/or machine learning (ML),¹³⁻²³ but only the work of Hong and co-workers claims explicitly the status of QSAR analysis.¹³ A common issue, however, is that, to the best of our knowledge, no study defines and reports the applicability domain (AD) of its predictive model. AD is the mathematical space where a model can be trusted to provide reliable and useful predictions, and it is an essential metric parameter in every trustworthy QSAR analysis.^{24, 25} The proper detection of the AD is a “hot” and ongoing challenging field of study in ML applied to material discovery, because the “black box” nature of ML methods does not allow the user to know when and whether the predictions are trustworthy.^{26, 27} Moreover, the lack of physico-chemical interpretability of the results reduces ML methods to “descriptive”, rather than “understanding” tools.²⁷

All published studies making predictions so far usually employ metric parameters like MAE (mean absolute error) and RMSE (root mean square error)²⁸ to assess the goodness in prediction, while omitting well-established fundamental QSAR metrics, like external Q^2 and concordance correlation coefficient (CCC) functions.^{28, 29} Notably, Q_{F3}^2 and CCC are considered the most reliable among them, since the former is independent from the evaluation set size and the latter is a measurement of precision and accuracy between experimental and predicted responses.²⁹

Another debatable aspect lies in the exclusive use of DFT-based variables (descriptors) when establishing relationship with experimental overpotential.¹³⁻¹⁵ There are mesoscopic and

macroscopic phenomena in material chemistry and design, in fact, that calculations of electronic structure alone cannot take into account, simulate or otherwise quantify.^{30, 31}

Last, but not least, all the predictive models proposed so far do not tackle the challenging aspect of model prediction in multi-material pools. To the best of our knowledge, in fact, each study focuses on, and thus targets, one specific class of materials, like perovskites,^{13, 16, 21, 22} spinels,¹⁴ Ni–Fe–Co oxides,¹⁷ metal hydroxides,¹⁸ metal alloys,²⁰ single atom catalysts,^{15, 23} multi-elements/high-entropy materials,^{20, 32} limiting both the predictive power and the applicability/“universality” of the models exclusively to the selected class in the training set. It goes unsaid that this limitation makes predictive models less appealing in industrial operational environments³³.

In the present work, we combine chemometrics and the codified and established rules of QSAR into the OECD principles and guidelines (Organization for Economic Co–Operation and Development for validation of QSAR models for regulatory purposes^{11, 25, 34}) and apply them to address the relationship between catalytic electronic and structural features and catalytic activity in terms of overpotential. Our approach provides an elegant solution to address all limitations of the multi-variate problem previously highlighted (lack of applicability domain and proper QSAR indicators, models built for only one class of materials, incomplete approach to the “multi-scale” nature of catalysis) with the clear intent to deliver a predictive and highly-accessible “multi-scale” model with interdisciplinary and multidisciplinary impact in heterogeneous (electro)catalysis, nanomaterials, cheminformatics, and sustainable industrial processes³³, in light of the new “safe and sustainable by design” concept.³⁵

RESULTS

All statistical analysis has been carried out using Real Statistics Resource Pack Software developed by Zaiontz.^{36,37} The organization of this study reflects the sequential block–diagram organization of the procedures and sub–procedures highlighted in Figure 1.

Figure 1. Flowchart of the work carried out in this work.

Exploratory analysis. The aim of the exploratory analysis is to provide an overview of the collected data without making any assumption(s).¹⁰ This phase includes data collection and data set creation (see Supporting Information (SI) at pages S–4 to S–24), descriptive statistics on the explanatory variables (see SI at pages S–25 to S–42), pretreatment of the data (see SI at page S–43) and detection of potential outliers (see SI at pages S–43 to S–44).

Data collection. Table 1 summarizes the protocols and criteria established to collect experimental and computational data (for details on the criteria, see the Methods section),

aiming at extracting relevant experimental data from the literature, allowing statistical evaluation of stochastic variables obtained from computational models (pre-scored against experimental comparisons) and, finally, reducing noise in the multivariate analysis. Importantly, the performances of a chemometric/QSAR model are more related with the quality of the data than the chosen chemometric method itself.^{25, 38} The established protocols also satisfy OECD principles.¹¹ Such principles are meant to guide and validate QSAR models for regulatory purposes, which comprise the clear definition of the endpoint of the model, the application of an unambiguous algorithm, the clear applicability domain (AD) of the model, the use of adequate measures of good-of-fit, robustness and predictive power, and, if and when possible, the elucidation of mechanistic interpretation.³⁴

Data set creation and descriptive statistics. The application of the protocols in Table 1 led to the “mining” of 44 OER catalysts (*i.e.*, 44 observations) from available scientific literature suitable for statistical evaluation, summarized in Table 2. These catalysts can be classified into five material classes (Figure 2A): perovskites (*e.g.*, ABO_3 ; 32%, 14 observations), spinels (AB_2O_4 ; 27%, 12 observations), delafossite (ABO_2 ; 16%, 7 observations), oxides (*i.e.*, simple oxides MO and MO_2 , with $M = d$ -block transition metal(s); 23%, 10 observations), and hydroxides ($M(OH)_2$; 2%, 1 observation). This trend reflects a more general tendency seen in literature: delafossites and hydroxides are less investigated than perovskites, spinels, and simple oxides as particulate OER catalysts.^{39,40} Moreover, hydroxides are also computationally difficult to model mainly due to their high structural disorder.^{41,42} Nevertheless, the dataset is very well-balanced for the presence of equally represented top catalytic contenders.

Table 1. Experimental and computational protocols applied in this study. A schematic figure of a three-electrode electrochemical cell employed in lab-scale OER measurements is also displayed where W.E.=working electrode, R.E.=reference electrode, C.E.=counter electrode.^{4, 6, 43, 44}

Experimental Protocol	Computational Protocol
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • QUANTUM ESPRESSO 6.8 (QE)⁴⁵⁻⁴⁷ calculation on bulks at 0 K • DFT+U_{eff}^{48, 49} with U_{eff} = 2.5 eV (Dudarev⁵⁰) • Spin polarization and collinear magnetic model • Ultrasoft (US) pseudopotentials⁵¹ • optb86b GGA functional⁵² • Monkhorst-Pack reciprocal space⁵³ with 0.20 Å⁻¹ spacing grid • Marzari-Vanderbilt-Devita-Payne smearing⁵⁴ 	

Table 2. Experimental stoichiometry of the OER catalysts (observations) studied in this work, experimental OER overpotential (η_{10} , mV) measured at 10 mA cm^{-2} , and reference.

#	Experimental Stoichiometry	η_{10}	Ref.	#	Experimental Stoichiometry	η_{10}	Ref.
1	$\text{LiCo}_{0.8}\text{Fe}_{0.2}\text{O}_2$	340	⁵⁵	23	IrO_2	272	⁵⁶
2	$\text{LaFe}_{0.5}\text{Ni}_{0.5}\text{O}_3$	340	⁵⁷	24	$\text{LaCr}_{0.5}\text{Fe}_{0.5}\text{O}_3$	390	⁵⁸
3	$\text{La}_{0.9}\text{CoO}_{3-x}$	380	⁵⁹	25	$\text{Ni}_{0.9}\text{Co}_{0.1}\text{O}$	570	⁶⁰
4	$\text{LaNi}_{0.96}\text{Ir}_{0.04}\text{O}_3$	280	⁶¹	26	NiO	430	⁶²
5	$\text{LaMn}_{0.5}\text{Co}_{0.5}\text{O}_3$	460	⁶³	27	LiCoO_2	470	⁶²
6	CuCoO_2	390	⁶⁴	28	MnO	510	⁶²
7	Mn-NiO_x	363	⁶⁵	29	$\text{Fe}_{1-x}\text{Ni}_2\text{O}_4$	270	⁶⁶
8	$\text{Ru}_{0.9}\text{Mn}_{0.1}\text{O}_2$	231	⁶⁷	30	NiFe_2O_4	455	⁶⁸
9	Fe_3O_4	352	⁶⁹	31	$(\text{Co}_{0.36}\text{Fe}_{0.64})[\text{Co}_{0.64}\text{Fe}_{1.36}]\text{O}_4$	484	⁶⁸
10	$\text{Ni}_{0.9}\text{Fe}_{0.1}\text{O}$	297	⁷⁰	32	$\text{Mn}_{0.25}\text{Co}_{0.25}\text{Ni}_{0.25}\text{Fe}_{2.25}\text{O}_{4-x}$	334	⁷¹
11	$(\text{Zn}_{0.36}\text{Fe}_{0.64})[\text{Zn}_{0.64}\text{Fe}_{1.36}]\text{O}_4$	500	⁶⁸	33	NiO_x	350	⁷²
12	$(\text{Co}_{0.5}\text{Ni}_{0.5})\text{Fe}_2\text{O}_4$	477	⁷³	34	LaFeO_3	510	⁷⁴
13	Mn_3O_4	430	⁶²	35	$\text{La}_{0.7}\text{Sr}_{0.3}\text{Mn}_{0.5}\text{Ni}_{0.5}\text{O}_3$	367	⁷⁵
14	$\text{LaMn}_{0.5}\text{Ni}_{0.5}\text{O}_3$	370	⁷⁶	36	CaCoO_3	260	⁷⁷
15	$\text{Ni}(\text{OH})_2$	299	⁷⁸	37	AgCoO_2	395	⁷⁹
16	LaNiO_3	446	⁸⁰	38	$\text{Ru}_{0.85}\text{Ir}_{0.15}\text{O}_2$	234	⁸¹
17	LaCoO_3	461	⁸⁰	39	LaCrO_3	540	⁵⁸
18	$\text{LiNi}_{0.8}\text{Fe}_{0.2}\text{O}_2$	330	⁸²	40	LiNiO_2	410	⁶²
19	SrCoO_{3-x}	290	⁷⁷	41	$(\text{M}_{0.10}\text{Fe}_{0.90})[\text{M}_{0.90}\text{Fe}_{1.10}]\text{O}_4$ (M=Zn, Mn, Ni, Co)	432	⁶⁸
20	AgFeO_2	317	⁸³	42	CoFe_2O_4	440	⁸⁴
21	$\text{LaMn}_{0.5}\text{Fe}_{0.5}\text{O}_3$	470	⁸⁵	43	$(\text{Ni}_{0.137}\text{Fe}_{0.863})[\text{Ni}_{0.863}\text{Fe}_{1.137}]\text{O}_{4-x}$	386	⁸⁶
22	RuO_2	230	⁵⁶	44	$(\text{Cu}_{0.082}\text{Fe}_{0.918})[\text{Cu}_{0.918}\text{Fe}_{1.082}]\text{O}_{4-x}$	369	⁸⁶

Figure 2. (A) Sample composition (in percentage frequencies) of OER catalysts studied in this work divided by material class. (B) Column chart, stacked by the material class, of the experimental OER overpotential at 10 mA cm^{-2} , distributed in 200–600 mV range.

As a preliminary straightforward guess for a possible explanatory variable (or descriptor), we tested the relationship between the catalyst material classes, shown in Figure 2A, and the experimental OER overpotential (response variable), shown in Figure 2B with distribution across intervals and respective frequency of appearance of OER overpotentials. Chi-square (χ^2) Pearson independence test has been used since the descriptor is a categorical non-continuous one and, in such cases, the correlation coefficient cannot be properly assessed. Pearson test can evaluate if two descriptors are independent, or associated, with each other.^{87,}

⁸⁸ The result of χ^2 -test shows that the descriptor “material class” and the response “OER overpotentials” are independent (p -value=0.18, α =0.05, see SI at pages S–30 and S–31), hence, the categorical descriptor has not been further evaluated for statistical analysis. Further explanatory variables, potentially affecting the experimental OER overpotential, have been collected through the application of the protocols in Table 1 and divided into three categories: those pertaining to **electrocatalysis**, to the **electrolyte**, and to the **catalyst** (Table 3). The variables (or descriptors) related with the latter contain both experimental (first seven variables) and computational descriptors (last five variables, see SI at pages S–14 to S–24), since many properties investigated in this category can be either difficult or impossible to

access by experimental means alone and/or may not be available for all OER catalysts within the selected statistical pool.

Table 3. The explored variables for electrocatalysis, electrolyte, and catalyst.

Variable	Type	Symbol	Unit
Electrocatalysis			
Catalyst loading	Continuous	m_{cat}	mg cm^{-2}
Use of binder/polymer in the suspension	Categorical	n/a	n/a
Type of binder/polymer	Nominal	n/a	n/a
Use of conductive additive in the suspension	Categorical	n/a	n/a
Type of conductive additive	Nominal	n/a	n/a
Type of electrode support	Nominal	n/a	n/a
Type of reference electrode	Nominal	n/a	n/a
Type of counter/auxiliary electrode	Nominal	n/a	n/a
Mass composition of the suspension	Continuous	m	mg
Resistivity of electrode support	Continuous	ρ	$\Omega \text{ cm}$
Geometric surface area of electrode support	Categorical	A_{geo}	cm^2
Application of $-iR$ correction	Categorical	n/a	n/a
Scan-rate used to record the polarization curves	Categorical	ν	mV s^{-1}
Tafel slope	Continuous	b	mV dec^{-1}
Current density at a fixed potential	Continuous	j	mA cm^{-2}
Specific activity	Continuous	j_s	mA cm^{-2}
Mass activity at a specific potential	Continuous	j_m	mA g^{-1}
Onset potential vs RHE	Continuous	E_{onset}	V
Electrolyte			
Type of electrolyte	Nominal	n/a	n/a
Electrolyte concentration	Categorical	$[C]$	mol L^{-1}
Hydrogenionic potential	Categorical	pH	n/a
Use of gas-saturated electrolyte	Categorical	n/a	n/a
Dynamic (or absolute) viscosity	Continuous	μ	mPa s
Double-layer capacitance	Continuous	C_{dl}	F cm^{-2}
Solution resistance	Continuous	R_s	Ω
Charge-transfer resistance	Continuous	R_{ct}	Ω
Catalyst			
Catalyst preparation method	Nominal	n/a	n/a
Type of d -element in catalyst	Nominal	n/a	n/a

Variable	Type	Symbol	Unit
Particle size by TEM/SEM	Continuous	d	nm
Brunauer–Emmet–Teller (BET) surface area	Continuous	S_{BET}	$\text{m}^2 \text{g}^{-1}$
Electrochemically active surface area	Continuous	$ECSA$	cm^2
Turnover frequency at a specific overpotential	Continuous	TOF	s^{-1}
Roughness factor	Continuous	f_r / R_f	n/a
Estimated Madelung energy	Continuous	E_M	eV
Estimated oxygen affinity	Continuous	ΔE_O	eV
Band gap	Continuous	E_g	eV
Estimated dipole electric moment per unit cell volume	Continuous	μ	D m^3
Atomic spin–only magnetic moments	Continuous	μ_B	μ_B

Nominal and categorical variables⁸⁸ seen in Table 3 have been also studied (see SI at page S–110 and S–123), but they have not been statistically explored any further at next steps (with the exclusion of pH), because the translation from their nominal/categorical code into a proper and useful numerical code is either impossible and/or very troublesome.

The next step of the exploratory analysis has been the careful choice of variables. Among all the experimental variables listed so far, only Tafel slope, catalyst loading, composition of the drop–casted suspension, pH and catalyst particle size have been identified as suitable for further statistical evaluation (see SI at pages S–4 to S–13). The statistical assessment of the other mentioned experimental variables is not possible since the experimental data are not available for all the observations listed in Table 2 (see SI at pages S–110 to S–123). It is pivotal to remark here that the excluded variables have not been removed based on their lack of influence on the electrocatalytic OER overpotential, which they may or may not have, but due to the lack of experimental data on the topic. The statistical assessment on their role cannot be carried out with a high confidence at this stage, but it may be carried out in expanded future works and/or in Design of Experiments (DoE), that specifically targets their role in influencing

OER overpotential in lab-scale experiments. Nine variables have been deemed statistically suitable and included in Table 4 of final descriptors.

Data pretreatment. The variables have been pretreated *via* regression assessment and transformation, and labelled with a unique ID code that allows easy recognition and cataloguing (Table 4). The use of transformed variable in statistics is necessary to guarantee reduction of skewness and kurtosis, stabilization of sample variance, normal distribution behavior of the variables and construction of models of superior robustness.⁸⁹ The transformations have been evaluated using the following statistical parameters: Akaike's Information Criterion (AIC), its modified version for a small sample size (AIC_c) and Schwarz Bayesian Criterion (SBC)⁸⁸. The results show that among all the possible models, the one built including all the transformed variables, delivers better performances (see SI at page S-43). Table 4 also shows corresponding regression correlation (r) and determination (R^2) coefficients with OER overpotential. r ^{87, 88} is a measure of the linear interdependency between two variables (for $r = -1$, all the data possess negative linear correlation, vice versa for $r = +1$, they possess positive linear correlation). R^2 is the square of the correlation coefficient^{87, 88} and it expresses the variance of the response variable (in this case overpotential) described by the n^{th} explanatory variable (for $R^2 = 0$, the explanatory variable does not explain any variance in the response, vice versa for $R^2 = 1$, the variable explains all the variance). Among all the variables listed in Table 4, the strongest correlation with the experimental overpotential is observed for experimental Tafel slope (**E4**, $r = 0.55$) and computational weighted average band gap (**C1**, $r = 0.54$), while experimental drop-casted suspension composition and computational Madelung energy variables have a correlation very close to zero (**E2**, $r = -0.03$, and **C3**, $r = -0.04$, respectively). The only variable exhibiting a sizable negative correlation with the overpotential is the pH normalized by the surface area of the OER catalyst (**E3**, $r = -0.13$). The remaining variables all display a weak positive linear correlation with the experimental overpotential

ranging between 0.11 and 0.35. Regarding coefficients (R^2), only experimental Tafel slope (**E4**, $R^2 = 0.31$) and computational weighted average band gap (**C1**, $R^2 = 0.29$) exhibit an appreciable value, indicating that each variables accounts only for $\approx 30\%$ of the variance in the response. A coefficient $R^2 \approx 0.30$, however, is considered low, especially for predictive purposes. This precious information led us to the conclusion that this multivariate problem cannot be solved, either in fitting or prediction, by a single dominant descriptor and that a regression analysis, using all the variables in Table 4 or combinations thereof, is required to deliver an effective predictive model. The values r and R^2 for non-transformed variables are reported in SI at pages S-40 to S-42.

Detection of outliers. Finally, our initial data set (44 observations in Table 2 by 9 explanatory variables in Table 4) is then searched and “combed” for potential outliers. Potential outliers have been identified primarily by applying the t-test,⁸⁸ which allows fast identification, but residuals,^{88, 89} Cook’s distance,^{88, 89} DFFITS (difference in fits),^{88, 89} and Williams plots⁸⁹ have also been employed to further assist and improve their identification and to detect possible influential points. Potential outliers have been eliminated from the analysis in an iterative way, until no outliers are anymore detected. Two outliers have been identified, Fe_3O_4 and $(\text{Co}_{0.36}\text{Fe}_{0.64})[\text{Co}_{0.64}\text{Fe}_{1.36}]\text{O}_4$ and, therefore, removed from the data set. The final data set has been reduced to 42 observations by 9 variables. Further information can be found in SI at pages S-43 and S-44.

Table 4. List of selected experimental and computational statistical variables, their corresponding ID code, and associated correlation (r) and determination (R^2) coefficients. GS: electronic “ground state”, calculated on bulk structures at open–circuit resting condition and neutral pH.

Variable category	Description and ID code	Formula of transformed variable	r	R^2
Electrocatalysis (exp.)	Estimated drop–casted catalyst loading onto surface area of working electrode	$E1 = \sqrt{\frac{m_{\text{cat}}}{A_{\text{work electr}}}}$	0.34	0.11
Electrocatalysis (exp.)	Weight % of binder and conductive additive masses	$E2 = \frac{(m_{\text{bind}} + m_{\text{add}})}{(m_{\text{bind}} + m_{\text{add}} + m_{\text{cat}})}\%$	-0.03	0.00
Electrolyte/ catalyst (exp.)	pH normalized for the surface area of spherical cat. particles	$E3 = \ln\left(\frac{\text{pH}}{A_{\text{cat}}}\right)$	-0.13	0.02
Electrocatalysis (exp.)	Tafel slope from Tafel plots	$E4 = \ln(b)$	0.55	0.31
Catalyst (comput.)	Weighted average band gap in GS	$C1 = \frac{(w_{\text{Eg}\uparrow} E_{\text{g}\uparrow} + w_{\text{Eg}\downarrow} E_{\text{g}\downarrow})}{w_{\text{Eg}\uparrow} + w_{\text{Eg}\downarrow}}$	0.54	0.29
Catalyst (comput.)	Mean value of absolute atomic spin–only magnetic moment in GS	$C2 = \frac{\sum(\mu_{\text{atoms}})}{n_{\text{atoms}}}$	0.29	0.08
Catalyst (comput.)	Estimated Madelung energy GS normalized at unitary volume in GS	$C3 = \ln\left(\frac{ E_{\text{M}} }{V_{\text{cell}}}\right)$	-0.04	0.00
Catalyst (comput.)	Oxygen affinity in GS	$C4 = E_{\text{catO}^*} + 1/2 E_{\text{O}_2} - E_{\text{cat}}$	0.35	0.12
Catalyst (comput.)	Estimated dipole electric moment per unit–cell volume in GS	$C5 = \sqrt{p \cdot V_{\text{u.cell}}}$	0.11	0.01

Modelling and Validation. Ordinary Least Squares regression (OLSR) workflow in Figure 3 has been selected as Multiple Linear Regression (MLR) method to deliver a predictive model for reliable lab–scaled OER overpotential predictions. OLSR, in fact, allows to find and describe functional relationships between explanatory variable(s) and response(s) by keeping

the physical meaning of the former ones⁸⁹ (which is the opposite of techniques like principal component analysis (PCA),⁸⁹ that guarantee orthogonality among descriptors, but at the expenses of physical meaning and clear scientific interpretation).

The regression analysis, starting from a matrix data set of 42 observations by 9 variables, has undergone two separate statistical treatments: workflow α , where the data set is split into training (36 observations) and internal evaluation sets (6 observations), and workflow β , where the data set is entirely used as training set (42 observations). For both workflows, the actual predictive performances of the resulting best models have been assessed by employing an external evaluation set built from six observations, collected according to the protocols described in Table 1. Most importantly, the observations included in such external evaluation set belong to a completely different and independent sample than that reported in Table 2. The use of such external evaluation set allows a more realistic evaluation of the prediction power of the models obtained from workflow α and β ^{24, 90} and also represents the future possibility to extend the application of the model⁹⁰ to new unexplored OER catalysts.

The validity of all the investigated regression models has been always checked through diagnostic methods, such as residual plots and Breusch–Pagan statistical test for homogeneity of variance (see SI at page S-24 and S-25 for further details). The regression analysis ends with the application of the best predictive model, obtained from the full training set obtained in workflow β , to predict the overpotentials of OER catalysts with unreported overpotential value (Figure 3).

Figure 3. Workflow of the regression analysis carried out in this work.

Results of workflow α The data set is divided into three iterative splittings to create three training sets and three internal evaluation sets composed of 36 (86%) and 6 (14%) observations, respectively. For comparison purposes, the size of the internal evaluation sets is equal to the size of the external evaluation one (6 observations) that will be presented in Figure 11. The splitting has been carried out by using k-means clustering algorithm (see SI at pages S-44 to S-52).^{10, 89} This phase resembles closely the well-known v-fold cross-validation⁹¹ when $v=3$, albeit, in our case, the splitting has not been done randomly.⁹¹

The following step, the variable selection phase, in Figure 3, has been carried out using different approaches, like evaluation of model parameters with QSAR criteria and thresholds, statistical significance testing (p -values in the ANOVA analysis are used as significance

criterion), and stepwise regression (a combination of forward and backward variable selection that iteratively chooses the variable subsets with the best prediction powers).⁹² Model robustness has been evaluated by using well-known Leave-One-Out cross-validation, Q_{LOO}^2 , as internal validation technique²⁸ for each regression model. The evaluation sets deriving from the splitting have been employed only as internal validation method to determine the internal prediction power of the regression models and it has not been used for building the models themselves and checking their stability (Figure 3).

The predictive power has been assessed by parameters Q_{F1}^2 , Q_{F2}^2 , Q_{F3}^2 , concordance correlation coefficient (CCC),^{28, 29} root mean square error of prediction (RMSEP) and mean absolute error (MAE).²⁹ Q^2 functions and CCC are QSAR parameters commonly used for predictive power and external validation.^{28, 29} Q^2 functions have similar formulation and meaning to R^2 and Q_{F3}^2 is considered the most reliable among them, since it is independent from the evaluation set size.²⁹ CCC parameter provides a measure of the degree of concordance between experimental and predicted data (trivially, the higher the value, the better the agreement).²⁸ In this work Q_{F3}^2 and CCC are selected as preferred QSAR parameters for comparing the predictive capabilities (internal and external) of the regression models investigated in workflow α and β . QSAR thresholds for model acceptance applied in this work have been regulated in compliance with the OECD principles: $R^2 > 0.70$ (fitting power), $Q_{LOO}^2 > 0.60$ (model robustness), $Q_{F1,2,3}^2 > 0.70$ (prediction power), $CCC > 0.85$ (prediction power).^{25, 28, 93} Williams plots (graphs plotting standardized residuals vs diagonal values of the *hat* matrix, h_{ii} = leverage) have been also built to outline the AD of the models²⁵, in compliance with the OECD principles. The AD defines a theoretical region, unique for each regression model, in the chemical space where predicted values can be regarded as reliable. Williams plot is a powerful tool for the identification of potential outliers particularly for ill-predicted values (response outliers) and for observations located outside the structural domain (SD) of the model

(structural outliers), both in training and evaluation sets. As a precautionary approach, only the models having 0–to–2 response and/or structural outliers have been selected in this work.⁹³

All the regression models evaluated in workflow α , and later in workflow β , are summarized in Figure 4.

Model ID	Variables/Descriptors								
	E1	E2	E3	E4	C1	C2	C3	C4	C5
A	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
B	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✗	✓
C	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✗
D	✗	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
E	✗	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✗	✗
F	✗	✓	✓	✓	✓	✗	✓	✗	✗
G	✗	✗	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✗	✗
H	✗	✗	✓	✓	✓	✗	✓	✗	✗
I	✗	✗	✗	✓	✓	✗	✗	✗	✗

Figure 4. Rows: regression models explored in this work with corresponding ID codes and contribution from variables. Columns: explanatory variables used to build regression models with corresponding ID codes.

Variable selection, based on the statistical parameters in Figure 5, has been carried out as first approach for identifying the best performing model, since it can provide a more complete overview of the regression results. All the models in Figure 5 exhibit good fitting power ($R^2 > 0.70$) and good internal stability ($Q_{LOO}^2 > 0.60$), with the exclusion of model I, whose $R^2 = 0.59$ and $Q_{LOO}^2 = 0.49$ fall far below the QSAR accepted thresholds.²⁸ All the models exhibit good predictive power with Q_{F3}^2 and CCC , ranging from 0.70 to 0.77, and 0.76 to 0.82, respectively, exception made for model I (Figure 5). Nevertheless, the best predictive model is E, with a

$Q_{F3}^2 = 0.77$ and $CCC = 0.82$ (QSAR threshold $\approx 0.85^{28}$). Model E is also the most robust model, with a $Q_{LOO}^2 = 0.72$, and the lowest RMSE value in both cross-validation and prediction. The R^2 adjusted for model E assumes the maximum value across the model series suggesting that model E exhibits the optimal level of complexity among the investigated models (see SI at pages S-66 and S-67). Furthermore, the results of the variable selection by statistical significance testing and stepwise regression (see SI at pages S-52 to S-66), point out that the model E has the best subset of significant variables. Therefore, model E has been selected for further assessment by using the external evaluation set.

Figure 5. QSAR parameters (including root mean square error of calibration (RMSEC) and cross-validation (RMSECV)) for fitting, robustness, and internal predictive power for all models assessed in workflow α . The displayed values are the average values obtained from the three iterative splittings (see SI at pages S-66 to S-70 for the values of each splitting).

The predictive power of model E in external validation drops, with average $Q_{F3}^2=0.59$ and $CCC=0.50$, respectively, but this trend is somewhat to be expected for two reasons: first, the model predictivity is overoptimistic at internal validation stage,^{24, 91} and, second, the external validation is always endangered by the limited data set chosen as evaluation set (6 observations in this case). The availability of data is a well-known limitation in efficient model validation,²⁴ particularly in the case of electrocatalysis, where the availability of coherent and consistent experimental data is scarce. Despite the obtained low Q_{F3}^2 and CCC values, however, Williams plots of 1E, 2E and 3E models (three-way splitting of model E) in Figure 6 show that the observations of the external evaluation set belong to the AD of the split model, indicating that the predicted overpotential values for such observations are reliable. Their leverages (h_{ii}) are below the critic value h^* , demonstrating that the probability of agreement between the predicted and true overpotential values is as high for the external evaluation set as that for the observations in the training set.²⁴ Moreover, since data falling outside of AD are classified as outliers,^{24, 89} the presence of one structural outlier in the internal evaluation set of model 2E and one response outlier in the internal evaluation set of model 3E can be detected in Figure 6. Since these outliers belong exclusively to the internal evaluation sets of 2E and 3E, however, they have limited relevance to the overall process of validation and prediction of model E.

In summary, the overall results presented for this workflow α confirm the finding that models A to H show excellent prediction of overpotential and good QSAR metrics. Model E, built with six significant variables (**E2, E3, E4, C1, C2, C3**), is the model with the best metrics overall, showing remarkable robustness and reliability, even in challenging external validation.

Figure 6. Williams plots and AD (yellow areas) for models 1E, 2E and 3E. The thresholds for response/structural outliers have been set to $-2.5\sigma < \text{standardized residual} < 2.5\sigma$ and to leverage $(h_{ii}) < h^*$ (changing for each model).

Results of workflow β . The full data set is entirely employed as training set here, entering directly the variable selection phase (Figure 3). The variable selection, fitting power, robustness, external predictive power, and applicability domain (AD) follows the same methodology, thresholds and leverage approach seen in workflow α . Figure 7 summarizes relevant QSAR parameters and criteria used to determine the fitting, internal stability, and external predictive capabilities of all the models presented in Figure 4, using the same external evaluation set employed in workflow α (see also SI at pages S-67, S-69, S-90, S-91 for further details).

Figure 7. Relevant QSAR parameters for fitting, robustness, and external prediction power for all models assessed in workflow β . Root mean square error of calibration (RMSEC) and cross-validation (RMSECV) are also reported.

All the models exhibit good fitting power ($R^2 > 0.70$) and good internal stability ($Q_{LOO}^2 > 0.60$), with the exclusion of model I, whose $R^2 = 0.59$ and $Q_{LOO}^2 = 0.51$ fall far below QSAR recommended thresholds.²⁸ All the models exhibit Q_{F3}^2 and CCC parameters below the corresponding thresholds of 0.70 and 0.85.²⁸ Q_{F3}^2 exhibit similar values across all the models, ranging from 0.59 to 0.64 ($\Delta = 0.05$) (Figure 7), while CCC values decrease from model E (0.50) to model I (0.19). Thus, the evaluation of the external predictive power in workflow β is better assessed by using the CCC parameter, since this parameter also provides a measure of the degree of agreement between the experimental values and the predicted ones.^{28, 29} All the models seem to have good predictive power and robustness (exception made for I), but model E displays the best combined metrics on predictivity and robustness, with one of the highest

CCC values ($CCC = 0.50$) combined with the highest $Q_{LOO}^2 = 0.73$ and the lowest RMSE in cross-validation (Figure 7). The external predictive power of model E, obtained here via CCC, is the same as that of model E obtained from the reduced training sets of 36 observations in workflow α . The R^2 adjusted for model E shows the same behavior seen in workflow α , assuming the maximum value for model E across the model series (see SI at page S-67). Moreover, the outputs of the variable selection, carried out by using statistical significance testing and stepwise regression, point out that model E is built with the best subset of significant variables (see SI at pages S-52 to S-63 and S-66).

Additional QSAR criteria, known as QUIK ($K_{XY} - K_X > \delta K$, $\delta K = 0.05$), R^P ($R^P > t^P$, $t^P = 0.05$) and R^N ($R^N > t^N$) rules, have been employed to check for multicollinearity,^{25, 94} redundancy and noise excess, caused by non-modelling noisy descriptors⁹⁴, respectively and the results have been summarized in Figure 8. Regarding the QUIK rules in Figure 8, models A, B, C and D exhibits values below the acceptance threshold ($t^P = 0.05$)⁹⁴, hence, the possibility of multicollinearity among descriptors cannot be ruled out in these models, and their performances should not consider trustworthy. Regarding the R^P rule in Figure 8, all models pass this rule, exception made for model A, for which $R^P = 0.05$,⁹⁴ indicating that, at least one variable injects redundant information into the model. R^N threshold (t^N) has been calculated as $t^N(\varepsilon) = (k\varepsilon - R)/(kR)$, for which one noisy descriptor is permitted (k = number of model variables, R = multiple correlation coefficient, $\varepsilon = 0.02$).⁹⁴ Regarding the R^N rule in Figure 8, only model I with $R^N - t^N = 0.47$ exhibits a value definitely above the threshold $R^N > t^N$,⁹⁴ suggesting that only this model has no overfitting caused by noisy variables.⁹⁴ This is somewhat expected, however, considering that model I has been built with only two variables.

Figure 8. Results of screening using QUIK, R^P and R^N rules on investigated models in workflow β .

Model G passes the test with $R^N - t^N = 0.01$, which cannot completely rule out the presence of excess of noise in the model. R^N rule is the strictest of the QSAR criteria used in this work and generally in literature.⁹⁴

Figure 9. Williams plot and AD (yellow area) for model E (top) and model G (bottom) built with the complete data set of 42 observations.

Reliability of the predictions has been again evaluated using Williams plot in Figure 9 with the same thresholds used in workflow α . The plot of Figure 9 shows that no response nor structural outliers are present in either the training and the external evaluation sets for both

models. Moreover, all the observations of the external evaluation set fall into the model AD, thus the predictions can be considered reliable. The overall results of workflow β agree with the ones obtained from workflow α : both approaches point out to model E (**E2, E3, E4, C1, C2, C3**) as the best performing predictive model. In workflow β , moreover, R^N rule suggests variable **E2** to be “noisy”, so model G has also been evaluated in this section. It is very important to mention that the results in workflow β highlight clearly that the roles, relationships, and “noise” of variables **E2, E3, C2** and **C3** with the response OER overpotential deserve further investigation using bigger datasets in training and external validation levels in future and more evolved statistical analyses.

DISCUSSION

Optimal model. After careful evaluation of the results of the variable selection methods and Williams plots coming from workflow α and β , models E (**E2, E3, E4, C1, C2, C3**) and G (**E3, E4, C1, C2, C3**) have been chosen and proposed as predictive models for the prediction of OER overpotentials under the described framework (for further information see SI at pages S-74 to S-79 and S-80 to S-85). Models E and G have been finally tested for the presence of chance correlation by carrying out the so-called Y-scrambling.²⁵ Y-scrambling shuffles the response variables n-times, destroying the mapping between the stochastic independent variables and the response variables and re-establishing a new mapping (such mapping is passed through the models without refitting), and compares average R^2 with the one obtained from the original unshuffled response. The presence of chance correlation between the model variables and the response is excluded, if the average R^2 from scrambled responses is smaller than the true R^2 of the model.⁹³ In our case, the overpotentials of models E and G have been shuffled up to 20 times and the calculated average fitting power is 0.18, and 0.15, respectively,

smaller than the original ones, $R^2 = 0.81$ and 0.77 (see SI at page S-68). This way, the presence of chance correlation in model E and G could be ruled out.

Model interpretation. OECD principles encourage QSAR modelers to provide mechanistic information and interpretations. Figure 10 shows the regression equations binding OER predicted overpotential to the significant explanatory variables **E2**, **E3**, **E4**, **C1**, **C2** and **C3** in model E. The use of standardized regression coefficients helps shedding light on the scientific interpretation of the model, since the weight of each variable is evaluated independently from their measurement scale.

$$\begin{array}{l}
 \text{Model E: } \eta_{10}^s(y^s) = -18.50 \mathbf{E2} - 27.18 \mathbf{E3} + 58.20 \mathbf{E4} + 40.67 \mathbf{C1} + 22.16 \mathbf{C2} - 36.23 \mathbf{C3} + 383.21 \\
 \begin{array}{ccccccccc}
 \swarrow & & \downarrow & & \downarrow & & \downarrow & & \downarrow \\
 \frac{(m_{\text{bind}} + m_{\text{add}})}{(m_{\text{bind}} + m_{\text{add}} + m_{\text{cat}})} \% & \ln\left(\frac{\text{pH}}{A_{\text{cat}}}\right) & \ln(b) & \frac{(w_{\text{Eg}\uparrow} E_{\text{g}\uparrow} + w_{\text{Eg}\downarrow} E_{\text{g}\downarrow})}{w_{\text{Eg}\uparrow} + w_{\text{Eg}\downarrow}} & \frac{\sum(|\mu_{\text{atoms}}|)}{n_{\text{atoms}}} & & & & \ln\left(\frac{|E_M|}{V_{\text{cell}}}\right) \\
 & \uparrow & \uparrow & \uparrow & \uparrow & & & & \uparrow \\
 & \mathbf{E3} & \mathbf{E4} & \mathbf{C1} & \mathbf{C2} & & & & \mathbf{C3}
 \end{array} \\
 \text{Model G: } \eta_{10}^s(y^s) = -27.41 \mathbf{E3} + 54.21 \mathbf{E4} + 40.22 \mathbf{C1} + 22.26 \mathbf{C2} - 34.23 \mathbf{C3} + 383.21
 \end{array}$$

Figure 10. Regression equations for model E (top) and G (bottom) with standardized coefficients and variable mathematical meaning.

The highest standardized coefficients belong to **E4** and **C1** variables in both regression equations (Figure 10). These variables are positively correlated with the overpotential, in other words, keeping the remaining variables constant, the lower the values of **E4** and **C1** the smaller the increments in the overpotential, and vice versa, the higher the values the higher the increments in overpotential. **E4** is the natural logarithm of Tafel slope (Table 4), an important electrochemical parameter related with the kinetics of the electrochemical process.^{95, 96} Tafel slope depends on several factor, such as catalyst mass, catalyst morphology and shape, surface coverage and electrochemical experimental conditions.^{97, 98} **C1** is the computational estimation

of the electronic band gap (Table 4). The band gap of a solid is the energy interval between valence and conduction band and it is commonly used to classify catalytic materials in good conductors, with a vanishing gap, and in bad conductors, with a wide gap.^{44,95} The size of band gap depends on several factors, such as electronic ground state of the catalyst, its magnetic properties^{68, 99}, catalytic composition and structural crystal system and defects. Good conduction properties in OER catalysts are known to facilitate the flow of electrons at the interphase between the electrolyte solution and the working electrode support.^{2, 95} In the limit of metallic conductors (*i.e.*, no band gap, as for state-of-the-art IrO₂ and RuO₂ OER catalysts), the contribution of **C1** to the overpotential vanishes and mainly **E4** is responsible for the overpotential increment. The trend uncovered by our model has strong physical meaning since, in general, low values of Tafel slopes and narrow (or, more so, zero) band gaps are experimentally associated with low overpotentials.^{2, 95, 100}

The standardized coefficients of **E2**, **E3**, **C2** and **C3** variables display lower weights compared with **E4** and **C1** in both regression equations of Figure 10. The negative sign of **E2**, **E3** and **C3** coefficients suggests a negative correlation between these variables and the overpotential. These three variables affect the OER overpotential in the opposite way compared to **E4**, **C1** and **C2**. Variable **E2** in model E, represents the experimental mass composition of the suspension drop-casted over the working electrode support (Table 4) and includes the drop-casted mass of the OER catalyst. Due to the negative correlation with the overpotential in Figure 10, it can be assumed that lower values of **E2** indicate higher amounts of catalyst mass, while higher values of **E2** corresponds to the opposite case (catalyst quantity in the suspension ≈ 0). This variable is subtly “Janus-faced”: from one side, an increment in catalyst mass generally induces a decrement in the Tafel slope in OER experiments (under the same electrochemical conditions)⁹⁷, and, from the other side, the formation of a thick layer on the working electrode support limits the mass transport and the reliability of Tafel measurements.⁴

¹⁰¹ Hence, the value of **E2** can never be either too high or too low. The strong physical meaning behind this variable seems to suggest that the catalytic quantity in the suspension should attain an “optimally balanced” value, high enough to allow optimal coverage of surface area of the working electrode support⁴, enhanced kinetics (connected to variable **E4**) and swift mass transport, and low enough to avoid the formation of thick layers at the electrodes presenting mass transport limitations. Regarding variable **E3**, the natural logarithm of the pH, normalized by the surface area of the catalyst (Table 4), reaches higher values for smaller particle sizes (e.g., 2–10 nm), independently from fluctuations in the pH of the electrolytic solutions. Therefore, the smaller the particle, the greater is the overpotential drop induced by **E3**. This effect has been experimentally recognized, since the reduction of the catalyst size provides more available catalytic surface area for OER to take place and an overall improvement of the catalytic performances.^{102, 103} **C3** represents the computational estimation of the Madelung energy of the bulk catalyst. Madelung energy is the electrostatic term of the total lattice energy of a solid, calculated by considering ions as fixed point charges in the solid structure.^{104, 105} The ionic or charge interactions in a solid depend on several factors, such as crystal system, presence and type of defects, and quantity and type of dopants.¹⁰⁴ The relationship between this variable and the OER overpotential is somewhat more difficult to describe, and, to our knowledge, availability of experimental data in this regard are limited. Nonetheless, high Madelung energies, hence high values of **C3**, can be associated to high stability of catalytic structure¹⁰⁴ (e. g., against leaching of dopants), beneficial charge polarization in M–O bonds, and facile adsorption of reactants to the catalytic surface thanks to electrostatic contributions.⁹⁵ One, or a combination of these effects, may easily explain the negative correlation with the overpotential in Figure 10. **C2** represents the average number of unpaired electrons per atom in the catalyst bulk. High values of **C2** are observed in spinel materials, while essentially null values are observed in catalysts, like IrO₂, LaNiO₃ and AgCoO₂. In the latter situation, the

contribution of **C2** in the model equation is null, thus, the positive increment in the overpotential due to **C2** is removed for such catalysts. **C2** mildly correlates (0.60) with variable **C3** (see correlation matrices in SI at pages S-74 and S-80), implying that the two variables are statistically linked. This aspect comes as no surprise, if we consider that ionicity, covalency and magnetism are interrelated phenomena, that depend on orbital population, occupation and polarization.^{99, 106} The standardized coefficient of **C3** is higher than the one of **C2** in both the regression equations shown in Figure 10, indicating that, for equal values of **C2** and **C3**, the negative contribution of **C3** weights more than the positive contribution of **C2** on the overpotential. The nature and the relationship of these two variables between themselves and with the OER overpotential are complex to describe at this level, and a more accurate description should be best left for future improved versions of the model featuring ampliations of the training set size.

The role of the equation intercept represents a baseline overpotential, a value from which the explanatory variables add or subtract their contributions. If all the variables were driven to 0, the baseline OER overpotential for this model would be 383.21 mV.

Predictions for “unknown-to-the-model” OER catalysts. The best performing models, E and G, have been employed to predict the overpotentials of “unknown” OER catalysts under the selected framework. These target OER catalysts have been selected randomly from the literature following protocols described in Table 1. They are: $\text{La}_{0.2}\text{Sr}_{0.8}\text{FeO}_{3-x}$ (perovskite),⁷⁴ $\text{Ni}_{0.8}\text{Ag}_{0.2}\text{O}$ (simple oxide),¹⁰⁷ $\text{CaCu}_3\text{Fe}_4\text{O}_{12}$ (perovskite),¹⁰⁸ $\text{Ir}-\text{Co}_3\text{O}_4$ (Ir-doped spinel),¹⁰⁹ $\text{NiCo}_2\text{O}_{4-x}$ (spinel),¹¹⁰ and $\text{Ru}_{0.94}\text{Co}_{0.06}\text{O}_{2-x}$ (simple oxide)¹¹¹. Figure 11 shows the prediction made with models E and G of their OER overpotentials, complemented with standard error (s.e.) of the prediction (in mV). Other information, such as 95% confidence intervals, 95% prediction intervals, can be found in SI at pages S-91 and S-92. It is worth stating clearly that the catalysts chosen here are “unknown-to-the-model” observations, for which the data and

OER overpotential values have been reported in literature, but never used at any phase of the construction of our model, from the fitting to the internal validation of model predictivity itself.

Figure 11. Predicted overpotentials values with corresponding standard errors in prediction versus experimental overpotentials (η_{10}) at 10 mA cm^{-2} (mV) for “unknown-to-the-model” OER catalysts.

Predicted overpotentials in Figure 11 show excellent agreement with experimental ones within remarkable average standard errors of prediction of $\pm 45 \text{ mV}$ for model E and $\pm 48 \text{ mV}$ for model G. The only catalyst that defies a nearly-exact prediction is $\text{Ni}_{0.8}\text{Ag}_{0.2}\text{O}$, for which a gap of about 100 mV is observed. We think that the source of this discrepancy may be attributable to the $-iR$ compensation that was never explicitly declared in the work.¹⁰⁷ Nevertheless, Williams plots in Figure 9 show that the predictions made by models E and G are reliable, since all of the “unknown-to-the-model” OER catalysts fit perfectly into the AD of the models (*i.e.*, no overpotential is statistically wrongly predicted). This analysis demonstrates also that the model

can be successfully applied for the prediction of OER overpotentials at 10 mA cm^{-2} under the selected framework.

Following orthodox QSAR protocol, we have also tested the model on two further “unknown” OER catalysts for which the experimental overpotentials have never been reported in the corresponding experimental works. These OER catalysts, selected randomly according to the protocols in Table 1, are: Ru–Co₃O₄ (Ru–doped spinel)¹¹² and CuO (simple oxide)¹¹³. Table 5 displays the results of such predictions.

Table 5. Prediction metrics from models E and G on the OER overpotentials of two “unknown” catalysts whose experimental values have never been reported.

Model	Experimental Stoichiometry	Predicted $\eta_{10} \pm \text{std. error of prediction (mV)}$	95% confidence interval (mV)	95% prediction interval (mV)
E	Ru–Co ₃ O ₄ <i>Fd–3m</i>	404.29 ± 43.00	382.52 – 426.07	317.01 – 491.58
	CuO <i>C1₂/c</i>	371.58 ± 45.59	333.89 – 409.28	279.03 – 464.13
G	Ru–Co ₃ O ₄ <i>Fd–3m</i>	390.81 ± 46.52	369.70 – 411.92	296.47 – 485.15
	CuO <i>C1₂/c</i>	345.04 ± 48.53	309.92 – 380.17	246.62 – 443.47

The reliability of the predicted responses, in other words the adherence of the new catalysts to the structural domain (SD) of model E or G, has been checked using Insubria plots in Figure 12. Insubria plot is a leverage–based graph of predicted values *vs* leverages (h_{ii}) developed by Gramatica and co–workers to verify the reliability of predicted values when no experimental data is available for the new observations.⁹³

Figure 12. Insubria plot containing the new “unknown” OER catalysts of Table 5. SD is colored in yellow area, defined by an arbitrary cut-offs of 600 mV (slightly higher than 532.72 mV and 542.78 mV, the highest predicted overpotentials in the training set for model E and G, respectively) and h^* .

The results in Figure 12 show clearly that none of the new catalysts fall outside of the SD and lead to the conclusion that also the predicted overpotentials for these new “unknown-to-the-model” OER catalysts can be considered reliable. We leave to future experimental studies the task of proving whether these predictions are reliable or erroneous.

CONCLUSION

QSAR strategies and OECD guidelines have not been yet fully applied to the domain of heterogeneous (electro)catalysis, partially due to the dynamic nature of the electroanalytical methods and the mathematical complexity required by the treatment of electrochemical data.

In this work, a QSAR model for the prediction of OER overpotentials in lab-scale experimental conditions (current of 10 mA cm^{-2} , particle solid catalysts, alkaline media, room temperature) has been proposed and successfully validated. The proposed models have been provided with a plausible interpretation and exhibits good fitting power and robustness. The models provide reliable predictions of overpotentials for new “unknown” OER catalysts (with an average standard error of the prediction of $\pm 45\text{-}48 \text{ mV}$) within the design of the study and the applicability domain of the models.

This work allowed the in-depth study of the role of several specific variables, and their combined effects on (electro)catalytic performances of OER catalysts, representing, to the authors' knowledge, the very first effort in the implementation of QSAR methods in heterogeneous (electro)catalysis. The methodology developed thereof can in principle be applied to new unexplored catalysts within the same reactivity pattern or entirely transferred to other heterogeneous (electro)catalytic reactions, without loss of meaning or validity. This work represents a starting point for future design of experiments (DoE) and statistical experimental designs aiming to reduce (or avoid entirely) time/cost-intensive OER lab-scale measurements, trial-and-error synthesis, and stability tests.

At present, the only limiting factors hampering further upgrades in terms of predicting power of this QSAR model, and perhaps its combination with machine learning and artificial intelligence (with the possible final goal of stand-alone software implementation), are almost exclusively related to data availability, such as (1) lack of explanatory variables related to both

experimental protocols and catalytic activity (most of the times, experimental data are not fully declared and/or reported consistently across data sources), (2) lack of complete experimental structural characterization of catalysts, which allows an accurate scoring of computational data.

METHODS

Lab-scale OER experiments are generally carried out at room temperature in a three-electrode cell^{4, 6, 43, 44}, in both alkaline and acidic media.⁴⁰ The electrode potential (E , in V) is commonly measured against reversible hydrogen electrode (RHE), or equivalent.^{3, 4} The experimental OER overpotential is simply the difference between the measured potential, recorded at a specific current density, and the equilibrium electrode potential (E_{eq}) of -1.23 eV under standard conditions⁵ (*i.e.*, $\eta_{10} = E - E_{\text{eq}}$).⁶ OER overpotentials are commonly reported at the given current density value of $j = 10 \text{ mA cm}^{-2}$.^{3, 4, 97} Only OER measurements carried out in alkaline media ($[\text{KOH}]_{\text{aq}}$ and $[\text{NaOH}]_{\text{aq}}$)^{40, 114} have been used in this work. The catalytic materials are usually deposited on the surface of the working electrode support. This process can be carried out through various methods such as deposition and precipitation^{115, 116}, although only the deposition of suspension by drop-casting technique has been considered in this work. The suspensions are generally composed of solid catalyst particles and volatile solvent. Binders/polymers (*e.g.*, silicon oil and Nafion®) and conductive additives/fillers (*e.g.*, carbon black and graphite) may be added to the suspension to enhance mechanical strength, electronic conductivity, and catalyst spatial distribution.^{44, 95} The catalytic materials selected in this work are all particle-shaped (powders, in the $0.5\mu\text{m} - 1 \text{ mm}$,¹¹⁵ or nanoparticles, in the $1 - 100 \text{ nm}$ range¹¹⁷), because they are one of the most investigated catalytic morphologies. Interest in them comes from how tuneable they are stemming from the wide range of experimental preparation methods and operating conditions.^{40, 115} In this work, data from electron microscopy (TEM and SEM) have been selected as preferred characterization techniques of particle size and structural

features, since they are the most used routine methods employed in catalysis.¹¹⁸ Only bulk properties have been investigated by DFT-based approaches vis-à-vis with experimental data, since catalytic surfaces are unstable and face drastic deconstruction and reconstruction during electrochemical reactions,⁹⁵ thus making the computational study of surfaces extremely problematic, dispersive and beyond the scope of the present work.

ASSOCIATED CONTENT

Supporting Information.

Data availability. All input files (.in), output files (.out) and .xml files, generated in Quantum Espresso, have been deposited in NOMAD database¹¹⁹ and they are available free of charge at the DOI: 10.17172/NOMAD/2026.02.19-2.

Author Contributions

Chiara Biz: conceptualization, investigation, formal analysis, methodology, data curation, validation, visualization, writing– original draft, writing– review & editing. **Mauro Fianchini:** conceptualization, investigation, methodology, writing– review & editing. **Nathan Daelman:** data curation, writing– review & editing. **Ramsundar Rani Mohan:** writing– review & editing. **Laura M. Salonen:** writing– review & editing. **Yury V. Kolen’ko:** writing– review & editing.

All authors have given approval to the final version of the manuscript. In compliance with ACS Ethical Guidelines to Publication of Chemical Research and for full transparency, the authors hereby declare that generative Large Language Models (LLMs), more specifically Claude Opus 4.5 from Anthropic, have been used *solely at the final review stage* to evaluate the writing

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Notes

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